

Provincial multistage power expansion planning toward coal and renewables positioning (Supplementary Information)

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I. MODELING OF PROVINCIAL MPEP MODEL

A. Macro-level Planning Constraints

1) Maximum Renewables Development Potential Constraints

Equation (1) ensures that the total installed capacity of renewable generating units does not exceed their maximum exploitable configuration potential.

$$0 \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} \leq Cap_i^{\max}, \forall i \in \Omega^{FRE}, y \in [1,6] \quad (1)$$

where $Cap_i^{\max}$ is the maximum installed capacity of unit i .

2) Generation Units Installed Capacity Continuity Constraints

Equation (2) models the expansion and decommissioning capacity changes of the unit, and further, (3)-(4) constrains the expansion and decommissioning rates of the unit. It is worth noting that (5) guarantees that the capacity of the transmission line at each stage is equal to that of the initial stage, which implies that the decommissioning of the transmission line is not considered in this model.

$$Cap_{i,y}^{total} = Cap_{i,y-1}^{total} + \Delta Cap_{i,y}^{inc} - \Delta Cap_{i,y}^{dec}, \forall i \in \Omega^{GT}, y \in [1,6] \quad (2)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta Cap_{i,y}^{inc} \leq \omega \times Cap_{i,y-1}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{GT}, y \in [1,6] \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{5}{N_{i,y}} Cap_{i,y-1}^{total} \leq \Delta Cap_{i,y}^{dec} \leq Cap_{i,y-1}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{GU}, y \in [1,6] \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta Cap_{i,y}^{dec} = 0, \forall i \in \Omega^{TL}, y \in [1,6] \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta Cap_{i,y}^{dec}$ is the decommissioning capacity of unit i at stage y , $\Delta Cap_{i,y}^{inc,max}$ and $\Delta Cap_{i,y}^{dec,max}$ are the upper bounds of the new and decommissioning capacity of unit i at stage y , respectively.

3) Carbon Emission Constraints

The total carbon emissions of each type of unit should meet the requirements of the carbon emission policy at each stage, as expressed in the following (6).

$$\frac{8760}{D_{\max} T_{\max}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{BG}\}} e_i P_{i,y,d,t} + \sum_{i \in \{\Omega^{CTG}, \Omega^{CBG}\}} (e_i P_{i,y,d,t} - E_{i,y,d,t}^{ccs}) \right) \leq E_y, \forall y \in [1,6] \quad (6)$$

where e_i is the unit carbon emission of generating unit i without CCUS, and E_y is the provincial carbon emission limit in stage y .

4) Water and Hydrogen Consumption Constraints

The consumption of raw materials for unit power generation is not negligible, and (7) and (8) give the total consumption limits for water consumption by the generating unit and

hydrogen consumption by the fuel cell subject to provincial areas, respectively.

$$\frac{8760}{D_{\max} T_{\max}} \sum_{i \in \Omega^{GU} \setminus \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} \eta_i^{wat} P_{i,y,d,t} \leq W_y, \forall y \in [1,6] \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{8760}{D_{\max} T_{\max}} \sum_{i \in \Omega^{FC}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} \eta_i^{hyd} P_{i,y,d,t} \leq H_y, \forall y \in [1,6] \quad (8)$$

where η^{wat} and η^{hyd} are the generating unit's water and hydrogen consumption per unit power, respectively. W_y and H_y are the provincial water and hydrogen consumption limits for stage y , respectively.

5) Capacity Reserve Constraints

For a specific region, the installed capacity of the generation units should be greater than the local peak power load to ensure the safe operation of the power system under an accident. The proportion of the excess capacity is called the generation capacity reserve ratio, so it is necessary to satisfy the power reserve requirement shown in (9). It means that the sum of the generation capacity of all generation units in the region and the capacity received from the DC line has to be in proportion to the regional peak power loads and the DC line sending out demand.

$$\sum_{i \in \Omega^{GU}} \alpha_i Cap_{i,y}^{total} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}} Cap_{i,y}^{total} \geq (1 + \beta) \left(\max_{d \in D, t \in T} L_{y,d,t} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,SEND}} Cap_{i,y}^{total} \right), \forall y \in [1,6] \quad (9)$$

where α_i is the generation capacity confidence level to measure the generation capacity of different units, β is the generation capacity reserve ratio, $L_{y,d,t}$ is the power load at the moment t of day d of stage y , $\Omega^{DC,REC}$ and $\Omega^{DC,SEND}$ are the sets of DC transmission lines in the studied area at the receiving end and at the sending end, respectively.

It should be noted that the sending end of the DC transmission line is supplied with delivered power by a dedicated generation unit, while the receiving end serves as a dispatchable unit so that the DC transmission line enables the transmission of reserve power in this model. In contrast, the AC transmission line determines the direction of power delivery according to the Area Control Error (ACE). Thus there are no defined receiving and sending ends, and the possibility of the AC transmission line's participation in the reserve is not considered in this model [1].

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B. Micro-level Operation Constraints

1) Provincial Power Balance Constraints

In this model, we consider hourly power balance as shown in (10).

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i \in \Omega^{GU} \setminus \{\Omega^{CTG}, \Omega^{CBG}, \Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}} P_{i,y,d,t} + \sum_{i \in \{\Omega^{CTG}, \Omega^{CBG}\}} P_{i,y,d,t}^{net} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{AC}} P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac} + \\ & \sum_{i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}} (P_{i,y,d,t}^{dis} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{ch}) - \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,SEND}} P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,send} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}} (1 - \sigma_i^{dc}) P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,rec} \\ & = \frac{L_{y,d,t} - P_{y,d,t}^{shed}}{1 - \sigma^{loss}}, \forall y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $P_{i,y,d,t}^{net}$ is the net output power of the unit with CCUS at day d time t of stage y , $P_{i,y,d,t}^{dis}$ and $P_{i,y,d,t}^{ch}$ denote the discharging and charging power of the energy storage unit at day d time t of stage y , respectively. $P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac}$ is the transmission power through AC transmission line i at day d time t of stage y considering line losses, in which a positive value represents the region as receiving power side, a negative value represents the region as sending power side. $P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,send}$ and $P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,rec}$ represent the transmitted power through the DC sending line i and the DC receiving line i at day d time t of stage y , respectively. σ_i^{dc} is the line loss rate of the DC line i , and σ^{loss} is the line loss and the network loss within the provincial area.

2) Transmission Line Net Power Balance Constraints

The annual net receiving or net sending power for provincial areas shall meet the actual operation as shown in (11).

$$\frac{8760}{D_{max} T_{max}} \left(\begin{array}{l} \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,SEND}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,send} \\ - \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} (1 - \sigma_i^{dc}) P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,rec} \\ - \sum_{i \in \Omega^{AC}} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac} \end{array} \right) = \frac{L_y^{net}}{1 - \sigma^{loss}} \quad (11)$$

where L_y^{net} is the net power send out of the provincial area through the transmission line for the whole year in stage y .

3) Load Shedding Constraints

Further, the region's load shedding power shall not exceed the region's power load, as shown in (12).

$$0 \leq P_{y,d,t}^{shed} \leq L_{y,d,t}, \forall y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (12)$$

4) AC and DC Line Power Transmission Constraints

Considering that the model proposed in this paper is oriented to provincial regions, we reasonably regard provincial regions as nodes of line power transmission, which can effectively avoid introducing complex power flow forms. On this basis, the power transmitted by AC and DC lines can be freely dispatched within the transmission capacity limits, avoiding the introduction of binary variables. In fact, this assumption has been widely used in grid planning at the national or provincial level [2], [3], when line losses will be proportional to the transmitted power.

Equation (13)-(16) gives the model of the AC transmission lines.

$$P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac} = (1 - \sigma_i^{ac}) P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,rec} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,send}, \quad (13)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{AC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,send} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{AC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (14)$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,rec} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{AC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (15)$$

$$-Cap_{i,y}^{total} \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \quad (16)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{AC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

where $P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,rec}$ and $P_{i,y,d,t}^{ac,send}$ are auxiliary variables to model the line loss of the AC transmission line, and σ_i^{ac} is the line loss rate of the AC transmission line i . It should be clarified that the AC transmission line is a bi-directional power flow, but the transmission direction is unique at a moment. In order to facilitate the modeling of line losses, the power flow direction at a moment is decoupled into the incoming and outgoing bi-directional power flows by introducing auxiliary variables in the form of this model.

Equation (17)-(18) is modeled for a DC transmission line, which differs from an AC transmission line in that a DC transmission line allows only unidirectional power flow.

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,send} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{DC,SEND}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (17)$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,rec} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (18)$$

5) Thermal Units Operation Constraints

Considering that the thermal power unit is an essential participant in the peak and frequency regulation of the power system, it is necessary to model its operation state accurately. When simulating the operation of thermal power units, we use continuous variables to characterize their start-up/shut-down states [4], which avoids the introduction of binary variables and can effectively improve the speed of model solving. Equation (19) is a lower limit on the capacity of thermal units, (20) simulates the variation of hourly on-line capacity, with upper and lower limits constrained by (21)-(22) to ensure that units start-up and shut-down satisfy the minimum start-stop time. Equation (23) limits the output power range of the units, and (24) is used to characterize the ramping characteristics of the units.

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, 0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{su}, 0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sd}, \quad (19)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} = P_{i,y,d,t-1}^{on} + P_{i,y,d,t}^{su} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{sd}, \quad (20)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} \geq \sum_{t=T_i^{su}}^{t-1} P_{i,y,d,t}^{su}, t > T_i^{su}, \quad (21)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} - \sum_{t=T_i^{sd}}^{t-1} P_{i,y,d,t}^{sd}, t > T_i^{sd}, \quad (22)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$\rho_{min}^i P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} \leq P_{i,y,d,t} \leq \rho_{max}^i P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, \quad (23)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

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$$\begin{aligned} -\delta_i^{rp} P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} &\leq P_{i,y,d,t} - P_{i,y,d,t-1} \leq \delta_i^{rp} P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, \\ \forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}$ is the on-line capacity of the thermal unit at day d time t in stage y , whose real-time output is limited by the on-line capacity. T_i^{su} and T_i^{sd} are the minimum start-up and shut-down times of thermal unit i , respectively. $\rho_{\min}^i$ and $\rho_{\max}^i$ are the minimum and maximum coefficients of the output of unit i , respectively, and δ_i^{rp} is the ramping coefficient of unit i .

6) Biomass and Hydro Units Operation Constraints

Considering the limited capacity of biomass and hydro units to participate in the power system and the fact that they are not easy to control compared to thermal power, the aggregation model is widely used for their operation, as shown in the following (25)-(26).

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\min}^i Cap_{i,y}^{total} &\leq P_{i,y,d,t} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \\ \forall i \in \{\Omega^{BG}, \Omega^{CBG}, \Omega^{HG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} P_{i,y,d,t} &\leq \frac{D_{\max} T_{\max} h_i}{8760} Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \\ \forall i \in \{\Omega^{BG}, \Omega^{CBG}, \Omega^{HG}\}, y \in [1,6] \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where h_i is the annual utilization hours of generating unit i .

7) Nuclear Units Operation Constraints

Similar to thermal units, the output power of nuclear units is also modeled using a continuum variable, as shown in (27)-(30). Considering the flexibility of start-up and shut-down of nuclear units, (31) further constrains the output power of nuclear units to remain constant during the day.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, P_{i,y,d,t}^{su}, P_{i,y,d,t}^{sd} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \\ \forall i \in \Omega^{NG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$P_{i,y,d,0}^{on} = P_{i,y,d-1,T_{\max}}^{on} + P_{i,y,d-1,T_{\max}}^{su} - P_{i,y,d-1,T_{\max}}^{sd}, \quad (28)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{NG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D$$

$$\rho_{\min}^i P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} \leq P_{i,y,d,t} \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, \quad (29)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{NG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$\sum_{d \in D} \sum_{t \in T} P_{i,y,d,t} \leq \frac{D_{\max} T_{\max} h_i}{8760} Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{NG}, y \in [1,6] \quad (30)$$

$$P_{i,y,d,t} = P_{i,y,d,t-1}, \forall i \in \Omega^{NG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (31)$$

8) Thermal and Biomass Units with CCUS Operation Constraints

Units installed with CCUS can effectively capture carbon. However, CCUS units are expensive, and the capture process will consume more power, so the net output of a unit with CCUS will be smaller than that of a unit without CCUS. The net output is shown in (32). CCUS units can change net output and carbon emissions by adjusting the intensity of carbon capture, modeled by (33). In addition, the operation of thermal and biomass units with CCUS is still subject to the constraints (19)-(26) of conventional thermal and biomass units, which are not repeated here.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{i,y,d,t}^{net} &= P_{i,y,d,t} - \lambda_i E_{i,y,d,t}^{ccs} - \eta_i^{ccs} Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \\ \forall i \in \{\Omega^{CTG}, \Omega^{CBG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq E_{i,y,d,t}^{ccs} \leq \mu_i e_i P_{i,y,d,t}, \\ \forall i \in \{\Omega^{CTG}, \Omega^{CBG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where λ_i is the power required for unit i to capture a unit of carbon dioxide, η_i^{ccs} is the fixed energy consumption coefficient of the CCUS device, whose fixed energy consumption is independent of the operating status and proportional to its installed capacity. μ_i is the maximum capture rate of the CCUS device.

9) Variable Renewable Units Operation Constraints

For intermittent generating units such as wind turbines and photovoltaics, their output during operation cannot exceed their maximum generating power, as shown in (34).

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq P_{i,y,d,t} \leq p_{i,y,d,t} Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \\ \forall i \in \Omega^{VRE}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where $p_{i,y,d,t}$ is the capacity factor of unit i at day d time t of stage y .

10) Fuel Cell Units Operation Constraints

Since the fuel cell possesses a millisecond-second dynamic response speed [5], [6], it can be modeled without considering start-up/shut-down constraints and ramping constraints, and its output power is shown in (35).

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \forall i \in \Omega^{FC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \quad (35)$$

11) Energy Storage Operation Constraints

Pumped storage and battery storage are considered in this model for energy storage, which have similar operation constraints. Equations (36) and (37) constrain the charging and discharging power and storage capacity of the energy storage, respectively, (38) characterizes the time continuity of the change in the storage capacity, and (39) ensures that the storage capacity achieves the short-term intraday balance.

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{dis}, P_{i,y,d,t}^{ch} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \quad (36)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq S_{i,y,d,t} \leq T_i Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \quad (37)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$S_{i,y,d,t} = S_{i,y,d,t-1} + \eta_i^{ch} P_{i,y,d,t}^{ch} - \frac{P_{i,y,d,t}^{dis}}{\eta_i^{dis}}, \quad (38)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$S_{i,y,d,t} = S_{i,y,d,t=T_{\max}} = 0.5 Cap_{i,y}^{total}, \quad (39)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D$$

where $S_{i,y,d,t}$ is the storage capacity of the energy storage device i at day d time t in stage y , T_i is the maximum charging and discharging duration of the energy storage device i , η_i^{ch} and η_i^{dis} are the charging and discharging efficiencies of the energy storage device i , respectively.

12) Spinning Reserve Constraints

Due to the uncertainty of load and renewable energy output, power imbalance may exist during the operation of the power system, and the system must have sufficient spinning reserve capacity to maintain the balance between power supply and demand. In this model, we only consider units that can adjust

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to the required output within 10 minutes to participate in the spinning reserve, as shown in (40).

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i \in \Omega^{GU} \setminus \Omega^{VRE}} P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}} P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \\ & \geq \tau_{load} \left(L_{i,y,d,t} + \sum_{i \in \Omega^{DC,SEND}} P_{i,y,d,t} \right) \\ & + \tau_{vre} \sum_{i \in \Omega^{VRE}} P_{i,y,d,t}, \forall y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where $P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr}$ is the capacity of spinning reserve available to unit i at day d time t in stage y , τ_{load} and τ_{vre} represent the spinning reserve coefficients of load and renewables, respectively.

Further, the capacity of each type of unit that can provide spinning reserve is represented by (41)-(48).

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} - P_{i,y,d,t}, \quad (41)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{TG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{on} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{net}, \quad (42)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{CTG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq \delta_i^{sp} P_{i,y,d,t}^{on}, \quad (43)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{TG}, \Omega^{CTG}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} - P_{i,y,d,t}, \quad (44)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BG}, \Omega^{HG}, \Omega^{NG}, \Omega^{FC}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{net}, \quad (45)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{CBG}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{dis} + P_{i,y,d,t}^{ch}, \quad (46)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq 6S_{i,y,d,t} \eta_i^{dis}, \quad (47)$$

$$\forall i \in \{\Omega^{BS}, \Omega^{PS}\}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,y,d,t}^{sr} \leq Cap_{i,y}^{total} - P_{i,y,d,t}^{dc,rec}, \quad (48)$$

$$\forall i \in \Omega^{DC,REC}, y \in [1,6], d \in D, t \in T$$

where $6S_{i,y,d,t} \eta_i^{dis}$ denotes the maximum power that energy storage device i can release in 10 minutes.

Notably, (48) indicates that the remaining capacity of the lines limits the spinning reserve capacity that DC transmission lines can provide. In the model proposed in this paper, the possibility of providing rotating standby for AC transmission lines is not considered due to the difficulty of scheduling AC line power flows within 10 minutes.

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II. CASE STUDY

A. Data and Parameters

TABLE SI

CARBON EMISSIONS, WATER, AND HYDROGEN CAP TARGETS FOR XINJIANG PROVINCE IN DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type (megaton)	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Carbon emission	162.68	115.47	62	35.50	7.94	0
Water	460.8	460.8	460.8	460.8	460.8	460.8
Hydrogen	0.0645	0.0915	0.122	0.151	0.178	0.209

TABLE SII

AC TRANSMISSION LINES CONSTRUCTED AND CANDIDATE IN XINJIANG PROVINCE

Status	Investment Cost (\$/kW)	Capacity (GW)	Lifetime (years)	Loss Rate
Constructed	131.13	10	40	0.83%
Candidate	176.19	20	40	2.00%
	188.71	20	40	2.00%

TABLE SIII

DC TRANSMISSION LINES CONSTRUCTED AND CANDIDATE IN XINJIANG PROVINCE

Status	Investment Cost (\$/kW)	Capacity (GW)	Lifetime (years)	Loss Rate
Constructed	279.95	8	40	7.20%
	399.22	12	40	7.00%
	334.85	24	40	6.50%
Candidate	295.83	16	40	6.50%
	325.66	16	40	6.50%
	280.47	16	40	6.50%
	317.08	16	40	6.50%
	333.26	16	40	6.50%
	322.10	16	40	6.50%

*All of the DC transmission lines in Xinjiang Province are designed to send power to other regions.

TABLE SIV

CAPITAL COSTS FOR VARIOUS GENERATION UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Cen-PV	912	803	723.84	676.8	650	577.92
Dis-PV	1002	960	920	882	845	810
On-WT	1437.5	1264.44	1142.4	1080	1010.4	970
Off-WT	2505	2324	2156	2000	1855	1721
BG	1338	1338	1338	1338	1338	1338
CCUS-BG	2837	2837	2837	2837	2837	2837
NG	6048	6048	6048	6048	6048	6048
HG	2821	2678	2561	2470	2405	2353
FC	2790	2052	1509	1110	816	600
BS	452	368	296	240	196	156
PS	608	608	608	608	608	608

*Units: \$/kW.

TABLE SV

CAPITAL COSTS FOR VARIOUS SINGLE-UNIT THERMAL UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type	Single-unit (MW)	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
TG	< 100	565	565	565	565	565	565
	100-200	530	530	530	530	530	530
	200-300	494	494	494	494	494	494
	300-600	477	477	477	477	477	477
	600-1000	459	459	459	459	459	459
	> 1000	440	440	440	440	440	440
	CCUS-TG	< 100	1118	1118	1118	1118	1118
100-200		1048	1048	1048	1048	1048	1048
200-300		978	978	978	978	978	978
300-600		944	944	944	944	944	944
600-1000		910	910	910	910	910	910

*Units: \$/kW.

TABLE SVI

MAINTENANCE COSTS FOR VARIOUS GENERATION UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Cen-PV	0.0193	0.0193	0.0193	0.0193	0.0193	0.0193
Dis-PV	0.0145	0.0145	0.0145	0.0145	0.0145	0.0145
On-WT	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192	0.0192
Off-WT	0.0244	0.0244	0.0244	0.0244	0.0244	0.0244
BG	0.0426	0.0426	0.0426	0.0426	0.0426	0.0426
CCUS-BG	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
NG	0.0348	0.0348	0.0348	0.0348	0.0348	0.0348
HG	0.0178	0.0178	0.0178	0.0178	0.0178	0.0178
FC	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
BS	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
PS	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025

*Units: proportion of the capital cost.

TABLE SVII

MAINTENANCE COSTS FOR VARIOUS SINGLE-UNIT THERMAL UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type	Single-unit (MW)	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
TG	< 100	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
	100-200	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
	200-300	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
	300-600	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
	600-1000	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
	> 1000	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153	0.0153
CCUS-TG	< 100	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305
	100-200	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305
	200-300	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305
	300-600	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305
	600-1000	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305	0.0305

*Units: proportion of the capital cost.

TABLE SVIII

OPERATION COSTS FOR VARIOUS GENERATION UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE YEARS

Type	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Cen-PV	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dis-PV	0	0	0	0	0	0
On-WT	0	0	0	0	0	0
Off-WT	0	0	0	0	0	0
BG	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643
CCUS-BG	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643	0.0643
NG	0.0061	0.0061	0.0061	0.0061	0.0061	0.0061
HG	0	0	0	0	0	0
FC	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025
BS	0	0	0	0	0	0
PS	0	0	0	0	0	0

*Units: \$/kW.

TABLE SIX

OPERATION, START-UP AND SHUT-DOWN COSTS FOR VARIOUS SINGLE-UNIT THERMAL UNITS

Type	Single-unit (MW)	Operation Cost	Start-up Cost	Shut-down Cost
TG	< 100	0.0382	0.1535	0.1535
	100-200	0.0358	0.1439	0.1439
	200-300	0.0334	0.1343	0.1343
	300-600	0.03225	0.1296	0.1296
	600-1000	0.0311	0.1249	0.1249
	> 1000	0.03	0.121	0.121
CCUS-TG	< 100	0.0413	0.1535	0.1535
	100-200	0.0387	0.1439	0.1439
	200-300	0.0361	0.1343	0.1343
	300-600	0.03485	0.1296	0.1296
	600-1000	0.0336	0.1249	0.1249

*Units: \$/kW.

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TABLE SX
LIFETIME FOR VARIOUS GENERATION UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT STAGE
YEARS

Type	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Cen-PV	28	30	32	34	35	35
Dis-PV	28	30	32	34	35	35
On-WT	25	27	28	29	30	30
Off-WT	25	27	28	29	30	30
BG	40	40	40	40	40	40
CCUS-BG	40	40	40	40	40	40
NG	50	50	50	50	50	50
HG	50	50	50	50	50	50
FC	8	11	12	13	14	15
BS	13	13	13	13	13	13
PS	50	50	50	50	50	50

*Units: years.

TABLE SXI
LIFETIME FOR VARIOUS SINGLE-UNIT THERMAL UNITS UNDER DIFFERENT
STAGE YEARS

Type	Single-unit (MW)	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
TG	< 100	40	40	40	40	40	40
	100-200	40	40	40	40	40	40
	200-300	40	40	40	40	40	40
	300-600	40	40	40	40	40	40
	600-1000	40	40	40	40	40	40
	> 1000	40	40	40	40	40	40
CCUS-TG	< 100	40	40	40	40	40	40
	100-200	40	40	40	40	40	40
	200-300	40	40	40	40	40	40
	300-600	40	40	40	40	40	40
	600-1000	40	40	40	40	40	40

*Units: years.

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B. Typical Scenarios Generation

Fig. S1. Typical scenarios for capacity factors of (a) Cen-PV, (b) Dis-PV, (c) On-WT, and (d) Off-WT.

Fig. S2. Typical scenarios for power loads in (a) 2025, (b) 2030, (c) 2035, (d) 2040, (e) 2045, and (f) 2050.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Zhuo, *et al.*, "Cost increase in the electricity supply to achieve carbon neutrality in China," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 3172, Jun. 2022.
- [2] G. He, J. Lin, F. Sifuentes, X. Liu, N. Abhyankar, and A. Phadke, "Rapid cost decrease of renewables and storage accelerates the decarbonization of China's power system," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 2486, May. 2020.
- [3] S. Chen, P. Liu, and Z. Li, "Low carbon transition pathway of power sector with high penetration of renewable energy," *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, vol. 130, pp. 109985, Sep. 2020.
- [4] X. Chen *et al.*, "Pathway toward carbon-neutral electrical systems in China by mid-century with negative CO₂ abatement costs informed by high-resolution modeling," *Joule*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 2715-2741, Oct. 2021.
- [5] N. Shaukat *et al.*, "A survey on electric vehicle transportation within smart grid system," *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 1329-1349, Jan. 2018.
- [6] A. Arsalis, P. Papanastasiou, G. E. Georghiou, "A comparative review of lithium-ion battery and regenerative hydrogen fuel cell technologies for integration with photovoltaic applications," *Renew. Energ.*, vol. 191, pp. 943-960, May 2022.